

The Homeric Hymn to Apollo

also known as "Homeric Hymn 3"

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Entry tags: Hymn, Religious Group, Text, Classical Indo-European, Indo-European, Ancient Greek text, Language, Greek Cult, Greek Religions, Graeco-Phrygian, Greek

The Homeric Hymn to Apollo (Homeric Hymn 3) is one of 33 ancient Greek hymns that were traditionally attributed to Homer, the semi-legendary composer of the Iliad and Odyssey. Today, scholars no longer believe that the Homeric Hymns were composed by the composer or composers of the Iliad and Odyssey, though the hymns do have important stylistic, narrative, and thematic affinities with the epics, by which they were probably partly inspired. The Homeric Hymn to Apollo one of the longer Homeric Hymns. Many scholars have argued that this hymn was originally two separate hymns, namely, a hymn to Delian Apollo that describes the origins and birth of the god on the island of Delos, and a hymn to Pythian Apollo describing how the god took charge of the oracle at Delphi. Others, however, have argued that the hymn was a unified composition. The archaic language of the Homeric Hymn to Apollo, particularly the first part of the hymn (the hymn to "Delian Apollo") has led scholars to argue for an early date of composition, perhaps as early as the middle of the seventh century BCE; the second part of the hymn (the hymn to "Pythian Apollo"), may have been composed later, in the early sixth century BCE. Walter Burkert has made the argument that the two parts of the hymn were first brought together in 523/22 BCE for a festival that the tyrant Polycrates of Samos celebrated on Delos (in accordance with instructions from an oracle, the festival would have honored both Delian and Pythian Apollo, and would have thus been an appropriate occasion for the unification of the two hymns if they were indeed originally separate).

Date Range: 655 BCE - 522 BCE

Region: Classical Greece

Region tags: Europe, Western Europe

Roughly the area encompassing the core of Classical Greek culture.

Status of Readership:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources and Corpora

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Chappell, Mike, "The Homeric Hymn to Apollo: The Question of Unity." In *The Homeric Hymns: Interpretative Essays*, edited by Andrew Faulkner, 59-81 (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2011)
- Source 2: Förstel, Karl, *Untersuchungen zum homerischen Apollonhymnos* (Bochum: Studienverlag Borckmeyer, 1979)
- Source 3: Miller, Andrew M., *From Delos to Delphi: A Literary Study of the Homeric Hymn to Apollo* (Leiden: Brill, 1986)

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://whc.unesco.org/en/list/393/>
- Source 1 Description: UNESCO's introduction to the archaeological site of Delphi
- Source 2 URL: <https://whc.unesco.org/en/list/530/>
- Source 2 Description: UNESCO's introduction to the archaeological site of Delos

Online Corpora

Relevant online Primary Textual Corpora (original languages and/or translations)

- Source 1 URL: <https://www.perseus.tufts.edu/hopper/text?doc=Perseus%3Atext%3A1999.01.0137%3Ahymn%3D3>
- Source 1 Description: Original text and translation of the Homeric Hymn to Apollo
- Source 2 URL: <https://chs.harvard.edu/chapter/8-the-homeric-hymn-to-apollo-translated-by-rodney-merrill/>
- Source 2 Description: Verse translation of the Homeric Hymn to Apollo by Rodney Merrill

General Variables

Materiality

Methods of Composition

– Written

Notes: The Homeric Hymns, including the Hymn to Apollo, were performed and to some extent also transmitted orally. Though composed within an oral framework and with oral poetic techniques (use of formulaic phraseology, traditional structures, etc.), the Hymns were also composed at a time when literacy was becoming widespread in Greece. Consequently, the hymns would have been written down from an early date, though it cannot be known exactly how soon after their composition they were written down.

Inked

– with Ink

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

– Papyrus

Was the material modified before the writing or incising process?

– Physical preparation

Was the text modified before the writing or incising process?

– Physical preparation

Location

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

– No

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

– No

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– No

Production & Intended Audience

Production

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

– No

Notes: Walter Burkert has argued that the hymn, originally two separate hymns, was first unified for a festival of Apollo on Delos funded by the tyrant Polycrates of Samos in 523/22 BCE; this unification of the hymn may have been achieved by the poet Cynaethus of Chios, sometimes cited in ancient sources as the author of the hymn. The composition of the text itself, however, was not funded by any specific polity.

Reference: Burkert, Walter. "Kynaithos, Polykrates and the Homeric Hymn to Apollo". *Arktouros: Hellenic Studies Presented to Bernard M. W. Knox*. Berlin: De Gruyter, 1979. p.53-62

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

– No

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– Yes

Reference: Janko, Richard. *Homer, Hesiod, and the Hymns: Diachronic Development in Epic Diction*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1982. p.93-94, 112-15

Archaic ritual language?

– Yes

Notes: The language of the Homeric Hymn to Apollo is very archaic, bearing important

linguistic similarities to the vocabulary, phrases, and formulae found in Homer and Hesiod. Whether this language is truly archaic or deliberately archaizing has been debated.

↳ Considered endogenous by the group itself?

– Yes

↳ Considered exogenous by the group itself?

– No

↳ Blended languages/creolizations/specific dialects?

– No

↳ Possess its own distinct written language?

– No

↳ If known: which authority (authorities) describe(s) the language as sacred?

[Select all that apply]

– Other [specify]: N/A

↳ Are non-religious institutions involved with the support of teaching religious language(s) for this text?

– Yes

↳ Are non-religious written languages used by the group's adherents to support religious study of text?

– No

↳ Are oral traditions used to support the religious study of the text?

– No

Intended Audience

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text

This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The Homeric Hymns were composed for oral performance, probably at public occasions such as religious festivals and/or large private gatherings or feasts at the houses of nobles. Consequently, it is impossible to determine the exact size of the audience typically present at performances of the

Homeric Hymns. If the Hymn to Apollo was performed at Polycrates' festival of Apollo on Delos in 523/22 BCE, then there would have been several thousand people present at that performance (see reference above); whether the hymn was even performed on this occasion, however, is completely speculative, and even if it were performed on this occasion it would have performed on other occasions as well (and on these other occasions we have no specific information).

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

– No

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

– No

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

– No

Notes: The Homeric Hymns were probably usually performed as prooimia, or preludes to longer narrative poetic (probably epic) performances. The context for these performances was probably connected with religious rituals (e.g., public festivals), but the Hymns themselves were not part of the ritual per se. The Homeric Hymn to Apollo, being one of the longer Homeric Hymns, was probably eventually performed independently, but there is no definite information regarding the contexts in which it was typically performed.

Is there material significance to the text?

– No

Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– No

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– Yes

Notes: The Homeric Hymns are known primarily from a handful of Medieval manuscripts, all from the fifteenth century. Earlier papyrus fragments supplement our knowledge of some of the hymns, though very few such fragments have survived for the Homeric Hymns. For more detailed discussions and references to the manuscript tradition in the context of the Homeric Hymn to Apollo, see the apparatus criticus of most modern editions of the Greek text.

↳ Are multiple versions viewed as proper?

– No

↳ Is there debate about which version is proper?

– No

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– Yes

Notes: The Homeric Hymn to Apollo is one of the Homeric Hymns (it is the third hymn in the collection).

↳ Is there a sense of canonization?

– No

↳ Is the text part of a series of volumes?

– No

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– Yes

↳ Cultural with religious implications?

– Yes

↳ Behavioral literature?

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: The Homeric Hymns were described in antiquity as *prooimia*, that is, poetic preludes performed to introduce longer poetic performances (especially epic performances).

Content

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary?
(Select all that apply)

– Vocabulary

Notes: The Hymn draws extensively on the vocabulary and phraseology of Greek epic, especially Homer

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– No

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– No

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– No

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– No

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– No

Notes: The text contains references to Tartarus, a personified being connected to the Greek afterlife, but does not make any explicit references to the afterlife or afterlife beliefs.

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dicated in the text?

– No

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– No

Are formal burials present in the text?

– No

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– No

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– Yes

↳ A supreme high-god is present

– Yes

Notes: Though Zeus, the supreme god of the Greek pantheon, does not play a central role in the hymn, he is present and is important as the father of Apollo (and of his twin sister Artemis)

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic or described in anthropomorphic terms

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld)

– No

Notes: Though Zeus was sometimes worshiped in a chthonic capacity, the hymn presents him in his more common Olympian (heavenly) capacity.

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god)

– Yes

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good

– No

↳ Other features of the supreme high god

– Specify: N/A

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world

– Yes

Notes: The text makes use of the epithet εὐρύσπια ("wide-seeing") to describe Zeus (line 339).

↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs

– No

↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region

– No

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region

– Yes

↳ Knowledge is unrestrict outside of sample region

– Yes

↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)

– Yes

↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)

– Yes

↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)

– Yes

↳ Knows basic character (personal essence)

– Yes

↳ Knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)

– Yes

↳ Has other knowledge of this world

– No

↳ Has deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

- ↳ Can reward
 - Yes
- ↳ Can punish
 - Yes
- ↳ Indirect causal efficacy in the world
 - Yes
- ↳ Exhibits positive emotion
 - Yes
- ↳ Exhibits negative emotion
 - Yes
- ↳ Possesses Hunger?
 - Yes
- ↳ Can be hurt?
 - Yes
 - Notes: There are myths that represent Zeus being hurt, such as some versions of the Typhon myth.
- ↳ Can be tricked?
 - Yes
 - Notes: There are myths that represent Zeus being tricked, e.g., the myth of how Prometheus tricked Zeus into accepting the inedible parts of animals for sacrifices.
- ↳ Can be imprisoned?
 - Yes
 - Notes: There are myths that represent Zeus being imprisoned, such as some versions of the Typhon myth.
- ↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural being other than the high god?
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature

–Specify: N/A

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life

– Yes

↳ In dreams

– Yes

↳ In trance possession

– No

↳ Through divination practices

– Yes

↳ Only through religious specialists

– No

↳ Only through monarch

– No

↳ Other form of communication with living

– No

↳ Does the text make communication with supreme high-god possible?

– No

Previously human spirits are present

– No

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings can be seen

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings can be physically felt

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world

– Yes

Notes: Apollo's role as an oracular god is strongly emphasized throughout the text. As an oracular god, Apollo naturally has extensive knowledge of the world and the future.

↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs

– No

↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region

– No

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region

– Yes

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region

– Yes

↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)

– Yes

Notes: Apollo's apparent ability to see people everywhere is illustrated by Apollo's perception (ἐνόησ', "he perceived," line 391) of a Cretan ship en route to Pylos as he searches for people to maintain his sanctuary at Delphi.

↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)

– Yes

↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)

– Yes

↳ Know basic character (personal essence)

– Yes

↳ Know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)

– Yes

↳ Have other knowledge of this world

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings can reward

– Yes

Notes: Apollo's appointment of the Cretan sailors as his priests can be understood as a reward.

↳ Supernatural beings can punish

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings communicate with the living according to the text?

– Yes

Notes: In the text, Apollo communicates with the sailors from Crete and has a dialogue with them.

↳ In waking, everyday life?

– Yes

↳ In dreams?

– Yes

↳ In trance possession?

– Yes

Notes: The Greeks believed that the Pythia, Apollo's priestess at Delphi, delivered oracles communicated to her while in a kind of trance.

↳ Through divination practices?

– Yes

Notes: The divination practices associated with Apollo at Delos and Delphi are alluded to in the text.

↳ Only through religious specialists?

– No

↳ Only through monarch?

– No

↳ Other?

–Specify: N/A

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature

–Specify: N/A

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– Yes

Notes: The second part of the hymn (the hymn to "Pythian Apollo") begins with Apollo ascending to Olympus and assuming his privileged place among the gods there as a son of Zeus, the leader of the Greek gods.

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model?

– Yes

↳ Organized hierarchically?

– Yes

↳ Power of beings is domain specific?

– Yes

Other organization of pantheon?

– Specify: N/A

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– No

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– Yes

Is the aspect of the supernatural being/high god visible to anyone in the text?

– Yes

Notes: There are several importance manifestations and epiphanies of gods in the text, especially Apollo. At the end of the hymn, Apollo appears to the Cretan sailors as a dolphin, and this epiphany is used to explain the name of Delphi (as coming from the Greek word for "dolphin" and thus commemorating this important epiphany of the new god of Delphi).

Is the aspect of the supernatural being/high god hidden from anyone in the text?

– Yes

Notes: When Apollo takes the shape of a dolphin in his epiphany to the Cretan sailors, he can be understood as disguising or hiding his aspect.

Are other categories of beings present?

– Other [specify]: Monster (the monstrous serpent Hera sends to fight Apollo at Delphi)

Does the text guide divination practices?

– No

Notes: The text alludes to Apollo's oracles at Delos and Delphi, but does specifically guide the divination practices associated with those sites.

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– No

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– Yes

Notes: At the end of the hymn, Apollo describes the punishment he will mete out to his new priests if they do not serve him properly. Earlier in the hymn, Apollo also punishes the nymph Telphusa for tricking him.

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known?

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god

– No

↳ Done by many supernatural beings

– Yes

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle

– No

↳ Done by other entities or through other means

– No

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known?

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence?

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce group norms?

– No

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness?

– No

↳ Done randomly

– No

↳ Other

– No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife?

– No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime?

– Yes

↳ Highly emphasized by the religious group?

– No

↳ Consists of bad luck?

– No

↳ Political failure?

– Yes

Notes: Apollo tells the Cretan sailors that other men will be their masters if they disobey him.

↳ Defeat in battle?

– No

↳ Crop failure or bad weather?

– No

↳ Disaster on journeys?

– No

↳ Mild sensory displeasure?

– No

↳ Extreme sensory displeasure?

– No

↳ Sickness or illness?

– No

↳ Impaired reproduction?

– No

↳ Back luck visited on descendants?

– No

↳ Other?

–Specify: N/A

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– Yes

Notes: In the first part of the hymn, Leto rewards the island of Delos by promising that it will forever be sacred to Apollo. Later, in the second part of the text, Apollo promises prosperity to his new Cretan priests at Delphi if they will obey and worship him.

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known?

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god

– No

↳ Done by many supernatural beings

– Yes

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle

– No

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence

– Yes

Notes: Apollo promises his new priests continued prosperity if they worship him properly.

↳ Done to enforce group norms?

– No

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness?

– No

↳ Done randomly

– Yes

Notes: Apollo's selection of the Cretan sailors as his new priests, if understood as a reward, seems to be random.

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife?

– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime?

– Yes

↳ Highly emphasized?

– No

↳ Consists of good luck?

– No

↳ Consists of political success or power?

– Yes

Notes: Apollo promises prosperity and political independence to his priests if they will obey him.

↳ Consists of success in battle?

– No

↳ Consists of peace or social stability?

– Yes

↳ Consists of healthy crops or good weather?

– No

↳ Consists of success on journeys?

– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure?

– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure?

– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health?

– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success?

– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants?

– No

↳ Other?

– Specify: N/A

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– No

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– No

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– No

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– No

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– No

Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require castration?

– No

Does the text require fasting?

– No

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– No

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– No

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– No

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– No

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– No

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– No

Notes: The text alludes to religious rituals held in honor of Apollo at Delos and Delphi and presents an aetiological account of the mythical origins of these rituals. However, the text itself does not prescribe any specific large-scale (or small-scale) rituals.

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– No

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– No

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– Yes

↳ Drama?

– No

↳ Comedy?

– No

↳ Tragedy?

– No

↳ Epic entertainment?

– Yes

Notes: Elements of the hymn, especially Apollo's battle with the monstrous serpent at Delphi, draws heavily on epic narrative style, themes, and techniques.

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– Yes

Notes: The text alludes to the practice of animal sacrifices in honor of Apollo.

↳ Are sacrifices specified by the text?

– Yes

↳ Animal sacrifice?

– Yes

↳ Human sacrifice?

– No

↳ Are there self-sacrifices specified by the text?

– No

↳ Are there material offerings present?

– No

↳ Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory?

– No

↳ Is the maintenance of the place regulated by the text?

– No

Notes: The end of the hymn describes how Apollo redirects a Cretan ship to Delphi so that the ship's crew can become his priests. He tasks his new priests with maintaining his sanctuary at Delphi. But the text itself does not specifically regulate the maintenance of the place.

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Society & Institutions

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– A city-state

Notes: The Greek world was split up into numerous city-states (or poleis) at the time that the Homeric Hymns were composed. It is uncertain in which city-state the Homeric Hymn to Apollo originated, though the author of the first part of the hymn seemingly refers to himself as a singer from the island of Chios, and the poem was sometimes attributed to the poet Cynaethus of Chios. Some scholars have also suggested that the poem was given its final form at the behest of Polycrates, the tyrant of Samos,

in honor of a festival held on the island of Delos (see references above).

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– Other

Notes: N/A

Are there specific elements of society involved with the destruction of the text?

– Other

Notes: N/A

Welfare

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– No

Notes: Though the text does not speak explicitly of institutionalized famine relief, Apollo does promise the Cretan sailors that they will never lack livestock in their capacity as the priests of Delphi, no matter how many animals they sacrifice to the god.

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– No

Other forms of welfare?

– No

Education

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– Yes

Notes: The Homeric Hymns seem to have been taught and to have been a subject of scholarly study in antiquity. They are still taught at universities today.

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– No

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– No

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– No

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– No

Is education gendered according to the text?

– No

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– No

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– No

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– No

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– No

Bureaucracy

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– No

Public Works

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– No

Taxation

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– No

Warfare

Does the text mention warfare?

– No

Food Production

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– Yes

Notes: Apollo assures the Cretan sailors that they will never lack livestock and food as long as they serve him faithfully at Delphi.

Does the text in question dictate how the religious group in question provide food for themselves?

– No

Does the text celebrate/restrict food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question?

– No

Which of the follow are forms of ritual food production [choose all that apply]?

– Small-scale agriculture/horticultural gardens or orchards

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